

without exudate, callus formation appeared 45 d after plating.

Using 15-20% towel gourd exudate in the induction medium increased anther culture efficiency in both japonica and indica rices.

Callus formed in that medium also had high plant regeneration (see table). Green plantlet regeneration reached about 90% in japonicas and improved significantly in indicas. Callus weights in the medium with 15-20% exudate were 5.7-18% higher than callus weight of the check after 10 d subculture. Fresh and dry weights of green plantlets increased by 2 and 89%, respectively. ■

Yield potential

Relationship of seedling shoot and root lengths and root number to rice yield and yield attributes

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We studied the effect of simulated seedling damage from uprooting and transplanting on performance of transplanted rice during late winter 1988-89 (variety IR64) and summer 1989 (IR50). The soil available N, P, and K were 286, 36, 219 kg/ha in the winter and 258, 47, 186 kg/ha in the summer.

Half the seedlings for the winter crop received 2 kg diammonium phosphate (DAP: 10% N, 46% P)/40 m² 10 d after sowing (DAS). Seedlings were transplanted 25 DAS. Treatments were no pruning, pruning roots to 1 cm, clipping shoots to 4 cm, and both root pruning and shoot clipping.

For the summer experiment, a uniform dose of 100:50:50 kg NPK/ha was applied. Seedlings measured on the average 22 cm shoot height and 6.5 cm root height, with 21 roots/seedling, and 0.07 g total dry weight. Treatments were no pruning, pruning roots to 1 cm, and moving some roots to leave 5, 10, or 21 roots.

In the winter crop, phosphate increased seedling height and weight but did not affect yield attributes or yield.

Root pruning increased plant height, tiller number, leaf number, and total dry matter.

Growth at 40 d after transplanting was reduced by shoot clipping (Table 1).

Seedlings with 10 roots produced more dry matter and grain yield than higher or lower root numbers (Table 2).

It appears that loss of roots and root injury caused by pulling seedlings do not affect plant performance, and may actually be beneficial. ■

Table 1. Effect of root pruning and shoot clipping on agronomic characteristics of the late winter rice crop, Tamil Nadu, India, 1988-89.

Treatment	Initial dry wt (mg/plant)	40 d after transplanting			
		Plant ht (cm)	Tillers (no./hill)	Leaves (no./hill)	Dry matter (g/hill)
No DAP					
Control	51.9	40.4	8.0	15.6	2.90
Root pruning	47.4	44.2	8.0	16.0	3.49
Shoot clipping	27.5	33.2	5.8	10.6	1.35
Root pruning + shoot clipping	23.0	34.1	6.0	10.8	1.49
With DAP					
Control	59.1	42.1	7.4	18.2	2.88
Root pruning	56.1	43.8	8.2	20.2	3.18
Shoot clipping	28.0	33.4	4.8	12.0	0.98
Root pruning + shoot clipping	24.9	34.4	4.6	12.4	0.98
LSD (P = 0.05)					
Fertilizer (F)	-	ns	ns	1.0	0.10
Treatment (T)	-	2.1	0.3	1.4	0.15
F * T	-	2.6	0.4	2.0	0.21

Table 2. Effect of root pruning on rice yield. Tamil Nadu, India, summer 1989.

Treatment	Productive tillers (no./hill)	Total dry matter (g/hill)	Grain yield (g/hill)
Without root pruning			
5 roots	13.4	35.25	19.70
10 roots	14.5	36.60	21.47
21 roots (all)	13.8	32.20	18.00
Mean	14.1	34.68	19.72
With root pruning			
5 roots	14.2	36.20	19.87
10 roots	15.0	36.35	22.52
21 roots (all)	14.1	32.60	19.23
Mean	14.4	35.05	20.54
LSD (P = 0.05)			
Root pruning (P)	0.3	ns	0.66
Root numbers (R)	0.4	2.25	0.81
P * R	0.5	3.18	1.14

Influence of low light intensity on production of high-density (HD) grain

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Low light intensity is an important constraint to wet season rice yields in the

tropics. Because grain weight is the major yield component, we studied the effect of low light intensity on the production of HD grain.

Ten long-duration rice varieties were transplanted in shaded (50% normal light intensity artificially maintained from 30 d after transplanting to maturity) and unshaded plots. Grain grade index was